

THE ROBOTS.TXT STANDARD – IMPLEMENTATIONS AND USAGE

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Extended Abstract

The robots.txt standard allows web masters to signalize operators of web crawlers how to best crawl their sites. The standard was initially proposed in 1994 [1] and is implemented in the following way: A file robots.txt is deployed in the root folder of a web site (eg. <http://example.org/robots.txt>). The text file is readable for web crawlers and contains policies how the crawlers (“robots”) shall access the site’s content. Access policies can be given for individual crawlers by “user-agent” name or by a wildcard rule block catching all crawlers not addressed in a named policy.

As a convention based on consensus not a legally binding regulation – the robots.txt standard nevertheless was adapted by all major web search engines and was extended in multiple ways to be able to specify

- the desired delay between successive requests to the web site
- more fine-grained access rules
- or rules for URL canonicalization
- the location of a sitemap [2] which allows to communicate to the crawler the exhaustive list of pages, images, videos, news pages while avoiding duplicates

The various extensions lead to differences how search engine crawlers implement the robots.txt standard. To further formalize the standard, in 2019 researchers at Google [3] submitted a RFC proposal [4] accompanied by a example robots.txt parser implementation [5].

The talk oversights the robots.txt standard as such and the varying extensions introduced over time. Starting with the perspective of a web crawler, we first look into actual implementations (eg. [5], [6]) of a robots.txt parser and difficulties matching rules and URLs.

We then analyze at the usage of the robots.txt in the web by web masters and site owners: which features or extensions are actually used, which crawlers are addressed as individual user-agents and is there a bias in favor of some search engine crawlers? We’ll use six years of archived robots.txt files from Common Crawl for our analysis and also compare these results with earlier work (eg. [7], [8], [9], [10], [11]).

We will also showcase examples how a polite crawler respecting the robots.txt standard can use the robots rules to optimize the implementation of URL queues.

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